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Introduction. Rational nutrition, high intake of iron inhibitors, chronic blood loss, vomiting disorders, chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, as well as the classification of the World Health Organization should be taken into account when doctors diagnose anemia. According to the WHO classification, the hemoglobin level is 110 g / l in pregnant women, 120 g / l in women, 110 g / l in children under 5 years of age, 115 g / l in children aged 5-12 years, 120 g / l after 12 years of age, and 130 g / l in men. forms. It is recommended to use the hemoglobin cyanide method in the determination of hemoglobin, which is a modern and reliable method.

According to UNICEF, one patient with iron deficiency anemia has 2 patients with latent iron deficiency, if the prevalence of anemia in the population is 40% or higher, then extensive prophylactic measures should be taken among at-risk groups. According to UNICEF

MODERN METHODS OF PREVENTING IRON DEFICIENCY IN WOMEN AND CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article scientifically substantiates and draws conclusions on modern methods of prevention of iron deficiency anemia in women and children living in the districts of Tashkent region.

recommendations, age-appropriate prophylactic iron supplements should be recommended once a week. Patients with severe anemia should first seek treatment and then continue prophylaxis. The advantages of taking iron supplements once a week are that the drug has no side effects, there is no need to conduct laboratory tests in the process of prevention, and less money is spent.

In order to solve the problem of anemia and prevent it, it is necessary to pay close attention to the following issues. Carry out large-scale advocacy work among the population, increase the knowledge of health workers about anemia, increase public awareness of the problem of anemia.

Based on the above, the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among women and children, the study of risk factors, their elimination, improvement of children's health, the development of measures to

improve the efficiency of medical care for children is one of the most pressing issues today.

The aim of the research. To study in depth the causes of the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia among women and children living in the districts of Tashkent region, to develop a set of measures to reduce them and to scientifically substantiate them.

Research material and methods.

One of the important tasks of the health workers of the Republic is to prevent iron deficiency anemia, timely recommend prophylactic doses of iron supplements among at-risk groups, recommend iron-fortified foods, explain nutrition. Taking measures before hemoglobin decrease, timely detection of iron deficiency, prevention of the development of severe anemia is one of the issues of economic and social importance for every family and society.

Although a significant reduction in maternal and child mortality has been achieved in our country, in some cases, ECGs are still a direct cause of maternal mortality or lead to serious complications

during childbirth. Anemia is one of these diseases. This is due, firstly, to the fact that it is widespread among women of childbearing age and pregnant women in the country (among all ECGs, it is 60-70% in some regions), and secondly, it adversely affects the birth process and causes various serious complications. This disease causes various complications during childbirth in 47.3% of cases. These figures are 90% in Karakalpakstan, 74.8% in Bukhara, 72.1% in Tashkent and 60.7% in Fergana. In particular, the dynamics of children with anemia in Tashkent region can be seen in the table below (Table 1). The analysis of childhood diseases was studied based on statistical data.

In 2018, anemia in Tashkent region has the following indicators, including 7.3% in China, 4.2% in Bostan, 11% in Boka, 28.6% in Parkent, 15% in Lower Chirchik, 61.3% in Zangiota, 37% in Bekabad, 37% in Piskent. 12.8%, Upper Chirchik 12.6%, Angren 18.6%, Bekabad 21.3%, Middle Chirchik 22.7, Chirchik 22.7%, Akhangaran 12.6%, Yangiyul 3.7%, Almalyk 35.9%, Akkurgan 23.2%, Kibray 55.0%. (Table -1).

Table -1

Indicators of anemia in children in 2018

Place name	Number of sick children, %	In terms of the number of children aged 0-14 (1000)	In terms of total population (1000)
Chinoz	7,3	34.3	122.2
Bostanlyik	4,2	40.3	149.9
Buka	11,0	31.1	111.6
Parkent	28,6	42.1	130.6
Lower Chirchik	15,0	26.6	98.3
Zangiota	61,3	98.9	317.0
Bekobod	37,0	37.8	147.5
Piskent	12,8	25.7	89.1

Upper Chirchik	12,6	32.4	118.4
Angren city	18,6	48.1	169.4
Bekabad city	21,3	26.7	89.1
Middle Chirchik	69,7	47.8	174.6
Chirchik city	22,7	35.0	143.9
Oxangaron	12,6	32.6	117.2
Yangiyul	3,7	66.9	233.8
Almalik	35,9	36.6	126.8
Akkurgan	23,2	26,6	94,1
Qibray	55,0	48,9	173,6
Total:		736,0	2609,8

The study of the epidemiology of anemia and the application of advanced modern methods of its primary, secondary and tertiary prevention in practice based on the results is a topical issue.

Among children aged 0-14 in 2020, this figure will increase from 7.3% to 17% in Chinaz district, from 4.2% to 7.9% in Bostanlyk, from 11% to 18.9% in Buka, and from 28.6% in Parkent. 13.7%, in Lower Chirchik district from 15% to 11.2%, Zangiota from 61.3% to 59.3%, Bekabad from 37% to 35.4%, in Piskent from 12.8% to 17.5% , In Upper Chirchik from 12.6% to 11.9%, Angren from 18.6% to 25.8%, Bekabad from 21.3% to 25.4%, in Middle Chirchik from 69.7% to 65.7% in Chirchik city from 22.7% to 59.3%, in Akhangaran district from 12.6% to 12.9%, in Yangiyul from 3.7% to 10.4%, in Almalyk district from 35.9% to 34.5%. % ga. In Akkurgan it can be seen from 23.2% to 21.4%, and in Qibray district from 55.0% to 53.6%.

It should be noted that the anemia rate was found to be slightly higher in Angren, Middle Chirchik, Chirchik and Zangiota districts than in other districts.

Given that pediatric morbidity was mainly due to primary morbidity, we analyzed the overall morbidity.

In 2019-2020, the incidence of diseases among children aged 0-14 years

decreased, (33.8%).

The decrease in the incidence of childhood diseases was due to the decrease in both acute and chronic diseases. The decrease in morbidity in children was mainly due to the following classes of diseases: circulatory system diseases (63%), skin and subcutaneous klechatki diseases (52%), respiratory diseases (44.3%), nervous system diseases (42 , 7%), ear and mammary tumor diseases (40.7%), infectious diseases (31.5%), endocrine system diseases (30.3%), congenital anomalies (18.1%). Among the nosologies of the above class of diseases can be seen a decrease in diseases such as myopia (na 22.1%), viral hepatitis B (na 88.1%), bronchial asthma (20.4%).

An increase in childhood illnesses (38.2%) due to injuries, traumas, external causes of illness calls parents, UAS, to awareness.

The increase in anemia among children (by 8.2%) is due to poor quality of children's nutrition, unregulated diet, excessive consumption of artificial mixtures.

The incidence of children aged 0-14 years did not differ significantly from the incidence of children aged 0-17 years. The first place was taken by respiratory diseases, which accounted for 63%. Also in

the next places in both children and adolescents in 2018 will be diseases of the eye and its auxiliary apparatus (6.8%), diseases of the musculoskeletal system (5.6%), diseases of the ear and udder (4.4%), diseases of the urinary system (3.6%), diseases of the digestive system (2.8%), diseases of the endocrine system (2.8%), diseases of the nervous system (2.8%) and infectious diseases (2.8%).

By 2020, no significant changes were observed in the structure of childhood illnesses. The first place is occupied by diseases of the respiratory organs, followed by diseases of the eye and its organs (11.1%), diseases of the musculoskeletal system (8.5%). Ear and mammary gland tumors ranked fifth, followed by urinary tract diseases. Diseases of the digestive system rose from 8 to 4 places, and diseases of the hematopoietic system rose from 13 to 11 places.

From 2019 to 2020, adolescent morbidity decreased by 13.4%. The lack of positive dynamics of adolescent disease is associated with the registration of a number of diseases: congenital anomalies (71.6%), tumors (41.5%), diseases of the musculoskeletal system (35.8%), diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs (25.8%). The following nosological forms were noted: anemia (177.4%), diabetes (68.5%), gastritis (46.2%).

There was a decrease in the incidence of children with ear and mammary tumors by 58.7%, diseases of the nervous system by 39.7%, diseases of the urinary system by 34.1%, and diseases of the eye and its accessories by 23.9%.

It should be noted that with age, both primary and general morbidity increase. The gap between childhood and adolescent morbidity rates is constantly

growing, and this is evident in common morbidity. In particular, in 2017 it increased 2.6 times in general morbidity, 1.6 times in primary diseases, in 2021 - 3.4 and 2.5 times, respectively (growth rate was 23.5%).

When we compare the incidence rates of children aged 0-14 years and adolescents aged 15-17 years by disease classes, we can see that in 2014, the incidence rates increased in all grades. Diseases of the circulatory system (9.1 times), diseases of the endocrine system (8.2 times), diseases of the musculoskeletal system (5.5 times), diseases of the digestive system (5.3 times) increased intensively with the growth of children. . It should be noted that anemia was reported 21.8 times, bronchial asthma 10.5 times, and gastritis 10.3 times in adolescents.

In addition, with the age of the child, diseases of the eye and accessory apparatus, diseases of the nervous system, diseases of the respiratory organs were recorded more than 3 times.

Adolescents are more likely to be diagnosed with diseases of the ear and its auxiliary apparatus, anemias with diseases of the digestive system.

Infectious and parasitic diseases (83.1%), skin and subcutaneous diseases (47.5%), and diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs (12.3%) decreased with age.

The health status of children in the rural health posts of Zangiota and Qibray districts of Tashkent region is characterized by a decrease in the number of diseases in 2018-2021.

The incidence of primary and general morbidity in children and adolescents is declining. Only in adolescents can the incidence increase in

recent years, but not in 2018 figures. It should be noted that the primary morbidity rates, as well as the overall morbidity rates of children aged 0-14 years, were lower than the morbidity rates of children aged 15-17 years. It has been reported that the incidence of children under one year of age has decreased.

In the structure of general diseases of children (except for diseases of the respiratory system) led diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue, diseases of the skeletal joint system, diseases of the urinary system. In the structure of children under one year of age are dominated by diseases of the digestive organs, congenital anomalies, infectious diseases.

There is an increase in anemia,

gastritis, diseases of the endocrine system among children aged 0-14 years. This is mainly due to the low quality of children's nutrition.

Conclusion. Enriching foods with iron-containing products is the most effective and inexpensive method. The results of this program will be felt in a few years. The amount of iron in iron-fortified foods covers only the physiological needs of the body.

Obstetricians and gynecologists should intensify contraceptive measures until women of childbearing age with TTK fully recover and are discharged from the dispensary.

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